

Fungicidal test : For fungicidal assay, the method of Montgomery and Moore¹² with a slight modification has been used. All the compounds were tested for toxicity towards *Drechslera nodulosa*. Six of them are found to be quite promising. The percentage of germination of conidia of the above test fungus during 24 hours is given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—PERCENTAGE OF GERMINATION OF CONIDIA OF *DRECHSLERA NODULOSA* AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF THE TEST COMPOUNDS

Sl. No.	Name of the compound	% of germination at 50 ppm.	% of germination at 20 ppm.	% of germination in the control
1.	1-Carboxyethyl-3-[<i>o</i> -methoxyphenyl]-2-thiourea.	18	40	95
2.	1-Carboxyethyl-3-[<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl]-2-thiourea.	20	60	95
3.	1-Carboxyethyl-3-[<i>m</i> -tolyl]-2-thiourea.	20	53	100
4.	1-Carboxymethyl-3-[<i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl]-2-thiourea.	15	40	100
5.	1-Carboxymethyl-3-[α -naphthyl]-2-thiourea.	5	37	98
6.	1-Carboxymethyl-3-[β -naphthyl]-2-thiourea.	0	20	95

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the Board of Scientific and Industrial Research, Orissa and Jnan Bigyan Parishad, Utkal University for research grant to carry out this investigation, and to Dr. A. Narayan, Department of Mycology, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology for his supervision in carrying out the fungicidal tests.

References

1. D. J. BEAVER, D. P. ROMAN and P. F. STOFFEL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 1236.
2. P. CHARPENTIER, U.S. Pat., 2545, 764; 1951.
3. A. K. SENGUPTA and A. K. RAMAKHYANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 727.
4. A. C. GLASSER and R. M. DOUGHEY, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1964, **53**, 40; *J. Med. Chem.*, 1966, **9**, 351.
5. E. D. WEINBERG, *Bacteriol. Revs.*, 1957, **21**, 46.
6. D. LIBERMANN, *Nature*, 1949, **164**, 142.
7. G. CONTRERAS and H. CORTES, *Inorg. and Nuclear Chem. Letters*, 1970, **7**, 639.
8. B. G. BENNS, B. A. GINGRAS and C. H. BAYLEY, *Appl. Microbiol.*, 1960, **8**, 353.
9. H. W. GAUSMAN, C. L. RHYKERO, H. R. HENDERLITER, E. S. SCOTT and L. F. AUDRIETH, *Bot. Gaz.*, 1953, **114**, 292.
10. S. K. ADDY and G. N. MITRA, *Phytopathology*, 1966, **56**, 485.
11. C. N. RAO and R. VENKATRAGHAVAN, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1962, **18**, 541.
12. H. B. S. MONTGOMERY and M. H. MOORE, *J. Pomol. and Hort. Sci.*, 1958, **15**, 253.

Studies in Complex formation of metal ions with N-phenyl-N'-2-Thiazolyl Guanidine

W. U. MALIK, P. K. SRIVASTAVA & S. C. MEHRA*

Chemical Laboratories, University of Roorkee, Roorkee

Manuscript received 31 October 1972; revised 27 August 1973; accepted 30 August 1973

FROM the existing literature it has been that although the reaction of metals with a number of biguanides¹ have been studied from the different aspects, the reactions with complex derivatives of the type N-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) guanidine have received little attention.

Their study is important since a few of them have found use in medicine. Four metals of physiological and biological importance, viz., Cu(II), Hg(II), Mo(VI) and W(VI) were therefore chosen to study complex ion formation. Preliminary experiments had shown that Cu(II) form a soluble complex, dark brown in colour while the remaining three, viz., Hg(II), Mo(VI) and W(VI) gave insoluble colourless compounds. Their composition were determined using appropriate physico-chemical technique.

Experimental

Reagents : Mercuric chloride, cupric nitrate (B.D.H.) of A.R. quality were used for the preparation of stock solutions. The strength of these solutions were determined gravimetrically by the usual methods.

Sodium tungstate and ammonium molybdate solution of pH 2.0 were prepared by adding requisite amount of hydrochloric acid. Fresh solutions were always used in order to avoid the effect due to by aging or hydrolysis. The strength of these solutions were determined gravimetrically by the usual methods².

N-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) guanidine solution was prepared in 70% alcohol.

Apparatus :

O.D. measurements were carried out with the help of Bausch and Lomb's 'Spectronic 20'.

Conductometric titrations were carried out with the help of Toshniwal conductivity Bridge (K = 44) using dip type conductivity coeff. Measurements were made at 30° ± 0.1° in water thermostat.

Amperometric titrations were carried out with the help of Toshniwal polarograph (India) using scalamp galvanometer (W.G.Pye) in external circuit. All measurements were carried out at 25° ± 0.1° in water thermostat. The capillary used has the following characteristics in the open circuit, $t = 3.5$ sec., $m = 5.54$ mg/sec⁻¹, $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 3.38$ mg^{2/3} sec.^{-1/6}.

* Present address : 337, Beheripur, Dargai Gali, Bareilly, (U.P.).

Procedure :

Vosburg and Cooper's² method was employed for knowing the number of complexes formed in the case of Cu(II). The plot of optical densities against wavelength gave a maximum at 430 m μ thereby showing the existense of only one complex.

The composition was determined by Job's method⁴ of continued variation as well as by the molar ratio method. For Job's method equimolar solutions of the metal and the chelating agent were mixed in different metal to reagent ratio and their absorbance measured against 70% alcohol as blank.

For the molar ratio method⁵, solution were prepared with a constant concentration of copper but with the varying ratio of the moles of the chelating agent to the moles of copper. The absorbance of these solutions were measured against 70% alcohol as blank. The curves show a sharp breaks at the molar ratio 1 : 2 as metal; chelating agent

Conductometric studies :

Both direct (cupric nitrate in the cell) and reverse N-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) guanidine in the cell titrations were performed at different concentration of the reactants sharp inflection point were obtained at the stoichiometric ratio) Cu : N-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) guanidine as 1 : 2.

Composition of insoluble complexes of Hg(II), Mo(VI) and W(VI) conductometric studies :

Both direct (mercuric chloride, amm. molybdate and sodium tungstate in the cell) and reverse N-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) guanidine in the cell titrations were performed at different concentrations of the reactants. Sharp inflection points were obtained at the stoichiometric ratio corresponding Hg : M-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) guanidine as 1 : 2, Mo : N-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) guanidine as 1 : 1 and W : N-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) guanidine as 1 : 1.

Amperometric studies :

Amperometric titrations N-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) guanidine and mercuric chloride were carried out using sodium fluoride (1M) as supporting electrolyte and 0.01% gelatin as maxima suppressar at a potential of -0.05 volt (obtained from the plateau of the polarograph of mercuric chloride).

Amperometric titrations between N-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) guanidine and ammonium molybdate or sodium tungstate were carried out using HCl (0.05M) as supporting electrolyte at a potential -1.0 and -0.8 volt for ammonium molybdate and sodium tungstate respectively.

Direct (mercuric chloride, ammonium molybdate and sodium tungstate in the cell) and reverse (N-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) guanidine in the cell) titration reveal the existence of 1 : 2 complex in case of Hg(II) and 1 : 1 in the case of Mo(VI) and W(VI) respectively.

References

1. P. RAY, *Chem. Rev.*, 1961, **61**, 313.
2. ARTHUR I. VOGEL, *A Text-Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis*.
3. W. C. VOSBURGH and G. R. COOPER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437.
4. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim (Paris)*, 1928, **2**, 113.
5. YOE and JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.

An attempted synthesis of Schmid's 2-Methyl-10-Methoxy- β -Brazanquinone

O. P. JHA.

Chemical Laboratory, Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur

Manuscript received 16 December 1972; revised 5 May 1973; accepted 17 August 1973

THE paper describes the synthesis of 3,10-dimethoxy- β -brazanquinone(V) employing Bentley and Robinson's method¹ and an attempt to utilize the reaction sequence for the synthesis of Schmid's 2-methyl-10-methoxy- β -brazanquinone^{2,3}. Thus, 1,3-dimethoxybenzene was condensed with *o*-methoxyphenylacetic acid to the hydroxyketone (I), which was then transformed into the corresponding phenoxyester (II). The phenoxyester then under went a smooth cyclization in presence of sodium methoxide to methyl-6-methoxy-3-(2'-methoxy)-benzyl coumarone-2-carboxylate(III), the latter upon hydrolysis and intramolecular cyclization afforded 3,10-dimethoxy-6-hydroxy- β -brazan(IV). Oxidation of hydroxybrazan with chromic acid gave the desired quinone(V).

However, adaption of this route for the synthesis of Schmid's quinone presented serious difficulties at an early stage. Thus, the desired benzyl ketone could not be obtained in the pure form by condensing *p*-cresylmethyl ester with *o*-methoxyphenylacetic chloride. Although a crude product was obtained giving the expected colour reactions, the compound could not be purified for further studies.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected and were determined in pyrex capillaries. IR spectra has been recorded on Perkin-Elmer infraoord model 237 in potassium bromide.

2-Hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl-(2'-methoxy)-benzyl ketone (I) :

o-Methoxyphenylacetic acid (2.75 g.) was converted into acid chloride by treatment with thionyl chloride (5 ml.) in dry carbon disulphide. This was then added to anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.2 g.) with cooling. A brown complex soon formed. At this stage, freshly distilled 1,3-dimethoxybenzene (2.1 ml.) in 5 ml. dry carbon disulphide was added. The mixture was then heated on steam-bath for 2.5 hr., cooled and worked up in the usual manner.